

Management Issues and Challenges in Recent Trends

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Abstract

It is a competitive business world. All corporate businesses are mainly focus only the thing "Profit". The profit can be achieved through only the customer satisfaction and efficient management. Managing the new trends, issues and including so many business concepts is more important for the successful running of a business. In this paper we mainly focus on the recent trends in management, because our business environment is not static. It is dynamic in nature. It is always changing, both internal and external. Best managing company must know the strategy to face the changing environment. Technology, politics, and other factors are considered as important thing in the business environment which affects our management. Due to changing environment so many new trends are emerging. Our organization structure must be flexible and have a capacity to face everything.

Keywords: Trends in business, issues, strategy, environment.

Introduction

The term "Management" means getting the things done through others. Management has three levels such as top, middle and lower level. Top management people mainly focus on making the strategic planning, middle level peoples act as a bridge between top management and lower level peoples and the lower level carry out the execution process. The main duty of middle level is to make tactical planning and implement through the lower level people. Lower level employees' duty is to finish the work assigned to them by the middle level managers. Their duty is to complete day-to-day operational work.

Wherever there is human activity, there is management. Without efficient management, objectives of the company cannot be achieved. Qualified and efficient managers are essential to utilize labor and capital of the organisation. The most important goal of all management activity is to accomplish the objectives of their enterprise. The goals should be realistic and attainable. Managers set realizable goals and then they take mastermind action on all fronts to accomplish them. It is possible through full support form middle and lower levels of management.

All human and physical resources must be efficiently coordinated to attain maximum productivity. Without coordination, no work would be accomplished and there would be chaos and confusion. Management must be equipped to face the changes in business environment given by economic, social, political, technological or human factors. There must be adequate training to the human resources, so that they can perform well even in critical situations.

Emerging Concepts f Management

1. Corporate Governance

Corporate governance refers to the structures and processes for the direction and control of companies. Corporate governance deals with the relationships among the management, Board of Directors, shareholders and other stakeholders. Good corporate governance contributes to sustainable economic development by enhancing the performance of companies and increasing their access to outside capital.

2. Matrix Mangement

Matrix management is a type of organizational management in which employees with similar skills are pooled for work assignments. For example, all engineers may be in one engineering department and report to an engineering manager, but these same engineers may be assigned to different projects and they have to report to a different department managers or a project manager while working on that assigned project. Therefore, each engineer may have to work under several managers to get their job done. This concept overlooks the principle of “Unity of Command”. Because a single employee has to work under two are more boss.

3. Human Resource Audit

A Human Resources Audit is a comprehensive method to review current human resources policies, procedures, documentation and systems to identify its needs for improvement and enhancement of the HR function as well as to ensure compliance with ever-changing rules and regulations. An Audit involves systematically reviewing all aspects of human resources, usually in a checklist fashion.

4. Six Sigma Practices

The term “Six Sigma” is widely used to refer all of the structured method for improving business processes. This method, called DMAIC which means Define, Measure, Analyze, Improve, and Control, is supported by an assortment of statistical tools. DMAIC is a statistical measurement tool of how well a business process is performing. A process that performs with “Six Sigma” can produces only with lower sigma level defects on every million production. Six sigma concepts have become popular as the standard for excellent process performance.

An organizational in which people make decisions based on data, look for root causes of problems, define defects based on customer, seek to control variation, track leading indicators of problems to prevent them from happening, etc.

5. HR Outsourcing

HR outsourcing is the process of sub-contracting human resources functions to an external supplier. Reviews of business processes have led many organizations to decide that it makes business sense to sub-contract some or all non-core activities to specialist providers

6. Balance Score Card

The Balanced Scorecard is a strategic planning and management system that organization:

- Communicate what they are trying to accomplish.
- Align the day-to-day work that everyone is doing with strategy.
- Prioritize projects, products, and services.
- Measure and monitor progress towards strategic targets.

The system connects the dots between big picture strategy elements such as mission, vision, core values, strategic focus areas and the more operational elements such as objectives, measures or key performance indicators, targets, and initiatives.

7. Total Quality Management

A core definition of total quality management describes a management approach to long-term success through customer satisfaction. In a TQM effort, all members of an organization participate in improving processes, products, services, and the culture in they work.

Total quality management can be summarized as a management system for a customer-focused organization that involves all employees in continual improvement. It uses strategy, data, and effective communications to integrate the quality discipline into the culture and activities of the organization. Many of these concepts are present in modern Quality Management Systems, the successor to TQM.

Types of Issues and Challenges

- Changing Organizational Perspective
- Globalization of Business
- Quality Assurance and Productivity
- Ethics and Social Responsibility
- Corporate Governance Innovation and Change

1. Changing Organizational Perspective

The perspective and thinking about the organization is changed a lot. During past organization was focused on inflexible, manager should be stable and job focused. There were permanent jobs. Staff work as per the command of the manager or higher level but now a days manger should be skilled. He should work on team or command a team. There are lots of temporary jobs.

2. Globalization of Business

The world economy is increasing global in character. Manager will be involved in the management of global organization. They will need to think globally and act locally. Today more than one fourth of all goods produced worldwide cross the national boundaries. So it is one of the main emerging challenges.

3. Quality Assurance and Productivity

Now a day, the qualities of the goods and services have become most important. There must be continuous improvement in quality. Quality improvement has no boundary. It is the race without final line.

4. Ethics and Social Responsibility

An organization should be responsible towards shareholders, employees, customers, society and nation. Now a day's social responsibilities has become compulsory. Fulfilling social responsibility is a challenge for management. The concept of corporate social responsibility has developed. Social responsibility means obligation of business organizations towards society community, people, share holders, etc. To provide quality product at affordable price, to develop more and more employment opportunities, to carry out different development activities in society, to control pollution are some social responsibilities of business organizations.

5. Innovation and Change Management

Management must pay attention on innovation and change. Otherwise, they would go out of business. Rapid innovations are taking place in technology, product and service. Product lifecycle is getting shorter and shorter. Product needs continuous improvement if the life span is to be made long. New ideas, new techniques, new methods are being innovated; there must be new inventions of ideas and new invention of product. Old and outdated product cannot satisfy customers.

Conclusion

Every management must make their organization structure as a flexible one and provide adequate training to employees to face changes in the competitive environment. If it has no capacity to cope up with the technology and emerging concepts, it cannot sustain in the global competition. So the management must analyze the environment frequently and also focus on the customers' taster and preferences. It is the main factor that determines the success of the business enterprise.

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